

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN REVISIT INTENTION AND FOOD TRUCKS IN KLANG VALLEY, MALAYSIA

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ABSTRACT

In order to examine the factors influencing revisit intention towards food trucks in Malaysia, a quantitative research study was conducted, based on a randomised sample of 379 Malaysian respondents. With the increasing popularity of food trucks in Malaysia, with many current, and future ventures towards the food truck industry, this study focused on the antecedents of revisit intention, using several established concepts, from brand image, brand loyalty, brand awareness, brand association and perceived price. By taking a quantitative approach, the examination of the factors influencing revisit intention was conducted through itemised surveys, based on previously established research findings, focusing on the reliability and validity of the items in question. After analysis through multiple linear regression, it was noted that all items measured were significant and good predictors of revisit intention, with further recommendations and research directions encouraged within the field of food trucks and its consumer base in Malaysia.

Keywords: *Revisit intention, food trucks, brand image, brand loyalty, brand awareness, brand association, perceived price, Klang Valley*

INTRODUCTION

Consumers of today are displaying their affinity to eating outside, usually in outlets that are conveniently located to their offices or homes (Euromonitor International, 2014). Changes in the lifestyles of urbanites, most prominent amongst young working adults and young families, have been observed in their dining out habits. In Malaysia, dining out is a common recreational activity, where people socialize, added on with the affordability of most food options available, together with the large variety of cuisine, especially in urban areas (Kueh & Boo, 2007). Some of these choices include, but are not limited to full-service restaurants, cafes, fast food outlets, hawker stalls and ‘mamaks’, highly popular Indian-Muslim diners (Euromonitor International, 2008). Of these options, food trucks are one of the latest food choices that has been made available to Malaysian consumers in recent years (Kueh & Voon, 2007).

Consequently, in this ever-demanding environment for outside food options, the Klang Valley has also experienced a surge in food trucks over the years, which only adds onto the options available for the urban consumers (Kueh & Voon, 2007). The food eating habits and changes in lifestyles (especially for eating outside) is observed the most amongst Gen Y (Bhuyan, 2011), which in turn, have somewhat, led the changes in the food market and its associated consumer trends. At the time of this writing, there are over 100 thousand food truck operators registered in Malaysia, providing a healthy, competitive market environment, while providing the diverse food options that are demanded by the Malaysian consumers (Emms, Sia & Stantons, 2009). The growth of these food truck operators in Malaysia highlights a

healthy and competitive market environment, being responsible for as much as 37% of the \$1.4 billion in road income recorded in Malaysia, as of the year 2011 (Jane 2013). In the Klang Valley alone, it is estimated that 5 additional food trucks open every month, adding onto the growing market demand.

The changes in food consumption, in terms of eating habits and the like, have been closely linked to urbanization, and the changes in lifestyles that comes with it (Bhuyan, 2011). In places like the Klang Valley, income and population growth, have been found to have increased the demand for food (Euromonitor International, 2008), leading to observable changes in food habits, food purchasing and consumption pattern, especially amongst Gen Y, a key consumer section for food service (Bhuyan, 2011). With global consumerism patterns highlighting the preference for informality and casual settings, many of these younger consumers (Gen Y) are also found to lead the changes in consumer directions here in Malaysia, with the support for alternative options such as food trucks (Athem Sightings, 2012). With the propensity of Malaysian consumers already being used to the concept of road-side stalls and kiosks, adding food trucks to the mix is not an altogether 'alien' concept, and has been adopted quite easily by locals (Emms, Sia & Stantons, 2009).

It is not to say that food trucks have not experienced stiff competition, especially in Malaysia, with its already large repertoire of food selections, with respect to market penetration and adoption. However, as market demands shift, with the propensity for Malaysian consumers to accept newly introduced food concepts (Njite, 2005), food truck operators are fast becoming accepted by the market at large, quickly becoming normalised by Malaysian consumers. The support for the inclusion of food trucks as part and parcel of the overall food industry in Malaysia goes so far as to have governmental support, with numerous recorded instances of government-linked promotions for this market niche (Muzamil & Fazlin, 2012). However, the question remains as to how the retention of customers, and repeated purchases from said customers can be gained sufficiently, leading to many research directions taken in consideration of revisit intention within the food industry (Han et al. 2009; Kim et al. 2009a, b; Kim and Moon 2009).

Prior research findings have made conclusions that revisit intention is at the heart of commitment or loyalty (Day, 1969; Jacoby and Kyner, 1973; Jarvis and Wilcox, 1977), although there have also been add-ons to the concept of revisit intention, liking it to be an affirmed likelihood to revisit the restaurant in both the absence and presence of a positive attitude (Evanschitzky & Wunderlich, 2006). Nonetheless, there remains much to be examined with respect to revisit intentions, and the antecedents that may provide such a phenomenon. Current-day literature on the revisit intention of food truck operators in Malaysia remains limited at best, due to the fact that this phenomenon is understudied in this country – especially considering the options of food choices already available to most Malaysian consumers. However, that is not to say that the food truck phenomenon should be overlooked, as food trucks are fast becoming a part and parcel of consumer demands within Malaysia (Emms, Sia & Stantons, 2009).

It is important to take note of the fact that the major antecedent of revisit intention is the level of satisfaction as it will affect customer return to the place again (Baker & Crompton, 2000). Therefore, it is important for organization to provide adequate level of satisfaction in order to retain existing customer (Fornell, 1992). When referencing real-world statistics, the National Restaurant Association has shown that consumer interest in visiting a food truck has “increased significantly (Stensson, 2011),” in Malaysia, but thus far, there remains to be limited investigation of the overall market adoption of food trucks in Malaysia. As a matter

of fact, despite the growing trend and consumer acceptance of food trucks in Klang Valley (Venner-Pack, 2014), the subject of food trucks remains to be a limited scope of research and study altogether. Researchers (Soriano, 2002; Chi & Gursoy, 2009) identify restaurateurs' inability to satisfy their customers' expectations and experiences as one of the main reasons for their slow growth – and in relation to revisit intention, this is no different. Past paper findings have also shown that restaurants seem to be finding great difficulty in determining customer expectations and experiences (Rosslee, 2009) as customers seek more for their money when spending at restaurants (Thornton, 2009) – yet another research direction that can be consolidated with the growth of food trucks, and their offer of alternative solutions to said expectations and experiences.

Within highly competitive industries like food and beverage (Amini, Darani, Afshani, & Amini, 2012), it is important to understand why customers return to their preferred food venues, which remains to be a disconnect in academic and industrial research on consumer adoption of food trucks in a market environment like that of Klang Valley. The Klang Valley has offered ample opportunities for the growth of food truck operators, from the variety of food offered, to the acceptance rate of the consumer market (Venner-Pack, 2014), although the concept is still relatively new here, and the understanding of the revisit intention for food trucks remain inadequate at best. Studies of brand adoption have shown that brand equity may play a major role in customer revisit intention (Evanschitzky et al., 2006), although there are those like Soriano (2002), who has made note of the fact that customers have their own reason whether to revisit to any restaurant in the future, from lifestyle choices, to stress, to (restaurant) environments and many more. Others have shown that positive memories and new attractions are just as important for revisit intention (Um, Chon, & Ro, 2006), while there is also the conclusions made by several past authors that the frequency of visits (to the establishment/restaurant) plays a major role in revisit intentions (Court & Lupton, 1997; Petrick, Morais & Norman, 2001; Sampol, 1996). Consequently, there is much room for further investigation and examination of revisit intention, and with that said, it is crucial for researchers to take empirically proven research directions in understanding the latest food phenomenon, such as that of food trucks in Klang Valley.

In considering the the factors that lead towards customers revisit intention in food truck outlets, the findings from this present study will attempt to draw a more fulfilling picture of the food truck industry and its growth here in the Klang Valley, with a focus on the consumers and their perspectives on the subject matter at hand. There is a significant need to address the limited literature on the overall subject of food trucks in Malaysia, together with the subject of revisit intentions alongside. By understanding the factors that are affecting customer revisit intention, marketers and food truck owners can plan and develop marketing strategies in order to meet and satisfy the customer expectation. In addition, after acquire the useful knowledge in understanding their target customers, organization are able to gain competitive advantage to compete with their rivalry in the same industry.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Intention is subjective judgments about how a person will behave in future and it usually serves as a dependent variable in many service research and satisfaction models (Boulding et al., 1993; Soderlund & Ohman, 2003). The study by (Teng and Kuo, 2011) defined revisit intention as repurchase intention and behaviours that demonstrate the willingness to recommend and disseminate positive information for a service provide. Others like Soriano (2002), claims that customers have their own reason whether to revisit to any restaurant in the future, from lifestyle choices, to stress, to (restaurant) environments and many more. There

are also those who have concluded that positive memories and new attractions are just as important for revisit intention (Um, Chon, & Ro, 2006), while there is also the notion that the frequency of visits (to the establishment/restaurant) plays a major role in revisit intentions (Court & Lupton, 1997; Petrick, Morais & Norman, 2001; Sampol, 1996). Consequently, there is little standardisation on the subject of revisit intention within the field, which leaves researchers with the opportunity to further develop this concept.

Customers that has received an excellent and memorable experience from the restaurant will form a favourable behavioural intention such as recommending the restaurant to others, spread positive word of mouth or become a loyal customer, which will ultimately lead to revisit intention (Boulding et al., 1993; Reichheld & Sasser, 1990). Besides, employees giving customer special attention and consideration will make customers feel unique and thus increase their behavioural intention (Bitner, 1990). Additionally, environment and entertainment of a restaurant will elicit customer affective response and thus influence revisit intention (Kim & Moon, 2009; Jang & Namkung, 2009).

Food service providers are encouraged to develop activities which generate close guest-host interactions to increase customer added-value, positive affective response, and lead to repurchase intention (Hemmington, 2007). Therefore, customer affective response serves as an importance mediator role, whereby the higher the affective responses of customers perceived during their dining experience, the higher the repurchase intention they would generate (Pullman & Gross, 2004).

Generally, repeat customers are more profitable than new customer acquisitions. To ensure customer will revisit to the restaurant, retaining customer would be the most important strategy to be used by restaurant because the cost of attracting a new customer is always greater than the cost of retaining existing customer (Fornell, 1992). Evidence from study of Chaudhry (2007) has proven that repeat customers generate over twice as much gross income as new customers. However, to gain a new customer will cost six to seven times more than to keep existing customers (Conklin, 2006).

Brand Image & Revisit Intention

Just as consumers form their perception of brands via the brand image, there is also a close association between brand image, and how this affects revisiting intentions, as noted by Chew & Jahari (2014), in the case of Japan's tourism for example. Just as it is important for consumers to have a good and positive psychological and emotional association with a brand, and thus, becoming the driving force behind brand equity as such (Burmam et al., 2008), this same association will also be able to impact behavioural aspects of the consumers, such as their intention to revisit the brand's establishment, venue, or purchase their products and services again (Ryu, Lee & Gon Kim, 2012). Based on these points, it is then just as equally reasonable to expect the very same perception of brand image that influences brand equity, to also then affect customers' revisiting intentions. Therefore, the following hypotheses are proposed for this present paper.

Brand Loyalty & Revisit Intention

As mentioned by Yoo, Donthi and Lee (2000), it is indeed much more harder (and expensive) for brands to reach out to new consumers, instead of retaining their older customers, and thus, the study by Supphellen & Nysveen (2001) reiterated this said effect by measuring the drivers of intention to revisit well known websites of well-known companies (brands) by consumers.

It was found in these past papers that with the presence of brand loyalty, it is more than likely for consumers to have the intention to revisit these brands over and over again. This sense of loyalty and the intention to revisit is made much more observable in the food and beverage industry as noted by Han, Back and Barrett (2009), whereby consumers' revisit intentions were measured on their favourite restaurants. In this case, it was found that brand loyalty, alongside other just as important factors, were responsible for these customers revising their favourite establishments, regardless of the presence of alternative. In this sense, it can then be proposed that brand loyalty plays a major role in both brand equity and revisit intentions, as proposed for this present paper below.

Brand Awareness & Revisit Intention

Consequently, the essential knowledge of a brand can also be associated with the potential for consumers to build their revisit intention in regards to said brands, as found by Kim et al (2009). The proposition of brand awareness, and thus, the association that consumers have built towards said brand via their own informed perception, having a role to play in creating positive brand revisit intention was studied at length by Chen and Myagmarsuren (2010), in the case of tourism involving Mongolia as a destination. With potential customers associating the brand with positive feelings or thoughts, it is much more likely for these said customers to generate revisit intentions, and thus, this present paper proposes that brand awareness not only affects brand equity through consumer perceptions, but also generates revisit intention as stated below.

Brand Association & Revisit Intention

The presence of strongly held favourably evaluated associations that are unique to the brand, and the implication of superiority over other brands are crucial to a brand's success. Not only does this provide the brand with the status and positioning of the said brand within the market, it also increases the chances of consumers supporting the brand over and over again (revisit intention). Yet, unless the brand has no competitors, the brand will most likely share some associations with other brands. Shared associations can help to establish a category membership and define the scope of competition with other products and services. The favourability and strength of a brand association can be affected by other brand associations in memory.

Perceived Price & Revisit Intention

Various studies have found that the perceived price is one of the fundamental determinants that affect customer satisfaction specifically in the restaurant industry (Iglesias & Guillen, 2004; Jani & Han, 2011; Lymperopoulos, Chaniotakis & Soureli, 2013; Ryu, Lee & Kim, 2012; Martin-Consuegra, Molina & Esteban, 2007). According to these studies, the customers' perceived risk is low if the restaurant operators set its pricing right to create customer satisfaction. The subsequent satisfaction or dissatisfaction that experienced by consumers in the restaurant will have a significant influence on revisit intention and brand loyalty. Based on these discussions, the present study proposes that: it is explainable to expect that the perception theory of perceived price influence the perception of consumers on brand equity, just as much as it influences revisit intention.

Research Objectives

The following research objectives were proposed for this current paper:

- RO1: To examine the relationship and influence of brand image on revisit intention towards food trucks.
- RO2: To examine the relationship and influence of brand loyalty on revisit intention towards food trucks.
- RO3: To examine the relationship and influence of brand awareness on revisit intention towards food trucks
- RO4: To examine the relationship and influence of brand association on revisit intention towards food trucks.
- RO5: To examine the relationship and influence of perceived price on revisit intention towards food trucks.

Hypotheses

Similarly, the following hypotheses were developed in association with the literature reviewed:

- H₁: Brand image has a positive relationship with revisit intention towards food trucks.
- H₂: Brand loyalty has a positive relationship with revisit intention towards food trucks.
- H₃: Brand awareness has a positive relationship with revisit intention towards food trucks.
- H₄: Brand association has a positive relationship with revisit intention towards food trucks.
- H₅: Perceived price has a positive relationship with revisit intention towards food trucks.

Framework

Figure 1.0 below highlights the framework for this current paper.

Figure 1.0: Conceptual Framework Model and proposed model

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

In order to investigate the relationship between brand image, loyalty, awareness, associations, perceived value and its impacts and effects on revisit intention, this current paper will be focusing on food trucks in Malaysia, with respect to the consumer perception on all measured variables in question. Utilizing a quantitative approach, this current paper will conduct a series of itemised surveys amongst Malaysian consumers in relation to the topic at hand. Centring on the direct attributes of revisit intention, this current paper has adopted its own originally created version of the measurement of revisit intention and has proceeded to investigate whether different measurement will influence the relationship of revisit intention amongst Malaysia's food truck consumers.

As referenced in the conceptual framework shown above in Figure 1.0, the independent variables for the present research are brand image, brand loyalty brand awareness, brand association and price, while the dependent variable is revisit intention. These items were adopted from previous researches that have demonstrated the statistical validity and reliability, and thus, feasibility and acceptability for further research. Respondents indicate their experience in a 5-point Likert Scale ranging from 1=strongly disagree to 5=strongly agree, a scale that has been adopted for all items within the surveys utilized in this current paper.

The dimensions of revisit intention were measured according to the work by Zeithaml (1996). The existing research conducted in the restaurant context further supports this theoretical argument. According to restaurant patron behavior research, CWB is one of the important motivations of patrons' dining out behavior (Carpenter, 2007; Finkelstein, 1989; Ha and Jang, 2010; Park, 2009; Tse and Peter, 1988). As such, when patrons experience high levels of CWB from their dining experiences, they tend to revisit the same restaurant in the future. In other words, when patrons feel that their quality of life has been improved from their dining experiences, they show higher revisit intention. All the variables were measured through five-point Likert scales.

Aaker (1996) defined brand image as a "set of brand association that are anything linked in memory to a brand, usually in some meaningful way" and can be defined as the perception about a brand as reflected by the cluster of associations that consumers connect to the brand name in memory. On other hand, Kotler (2006) defined brand image as "a set of beliefs held about a particular brand". Among few studies aiming to fill this gap, (Kim et al. 2008a) argue that the combination of brand association and brand awareness has a positive impact on customers' behavioural loyalty. Brand loyalty was measured utilizing items from Kim and Kim's (2004) study, with four items for brand loyalty.

All items utilized to measure the constructs of research interest were derived from prior studies and contextualized for this current paper's food trucks. This study adopted items from Sun and Ghiselli's (2010) study to measure brand awareness with three items for brand awareness. To assess brand associations, we used different items that were previously used by different researchers (Aaker, 1996; Pappu et al., 2005). There exist three main perspectives on revisit intention. These include the notions of revisit intention as: a set of cognitive associations (Aaker 1991, Keller 1993, 2002), a price or revenue premium compared to a benchmark competitor (Aaker 1991, Ailawadi et al 2003), and a stock price premium (Simon and Sullivan 1993). These three perspectives on the meaning of revisit

intention have given rise to a multitude of proposed revisit intention measures in the academic arena, these three questions were imposed on price factors.

The survey instrument comprises of two parts: Part A and Part B and. The total items contained in the questionnaire and most of these items were closed-ended questions. Part A probe questions regarding the measurement adapted from previous publishes work with necessary wording changes to fit the revisit intention on food truck. The measures used in the study were drawn from the previous studies on revisit intention, brand image, brand awareness, brand association, brand loyalty, and perceived price. These questions are assessed directly on a 5-point Liker Scale which ranges from 'strongly disagree' to 'strongly agree'.

Part B is designed to capture information regarding respondents' demographic characteristics. These questions include the gender, age, ethnicity, education level, income and occupation of the respondents. The questionnaire respondents were filtered and were only filled by Malaysians of Klang valley.

Sampling

The respondents of the research were general adults aged above 18 years old. There were no demographic restrictions such as gender, age, ethnics and marital status for the participants. The respondents were voluntarily participated in the survey of research. Roasoft.inc 2004 uses a formula to provide a more accurate calculation, taking into account the margin of error as well as critical value for the confidence level. The accepted margin of error for the current study is 5%, whereby the confidence level is at 95%. Referring to Roasoft.inc, a minimum sample size of Malaysian population of 31.62 million residences should be 385. For this research, the researcher collected random samples among students, working adults and retired people. It will not be possible to get all food truck diners or who have experienced from Malaysia's Klang valley areas, so a non-probability sampling was used. A convenience sample was made. Sampling was be done through handing out the questionnaire which was done through Google questionnaire spreadsheet and hardcopy and collecting them on-site of operating food trucks. Accordingly, a total of 379 valid responded questionnaires were obtained, the respondents were found to have provided a valid response, to be used in this section to conduct statistical analyses. As noted by Blair and Conrad (2011), a sample size of a minimum of 200 were required to fulfil the appropriate sample size relative to a quantitative research paper such as this present one. All in all, a total of 1000 questionnaires were distributed both online and offline, to ensure that a high response rate can be found.

Data Collection

According to Hussey and Hussey (1997) all research has a primary stage which they must pass through and this include; Defining the research problem, Determining the concept of the research, Collecting the necessary data for the research, Analysing and interpreting the research data, stating the findings and recommendations. Digital questionnaires were distributed through Google questionnaire form and by distributing hardcopies to participants.

In this research, a total number of 1000 of questionnaires were distributed. As a result, 379 respondents were successfully gathered. The questionnaires were sent out and received between 10 July 2017 and 21 July 2017. At the beginning of the questionnaire, the objective of current study, general instructions, assurance of the confidentiality of respondents' feedback were mentioned clearly. All the respondents were informed that their

involvement in current study is voluntary and without any obligations. In addition, all the information provided will be kept confidential and used solely for research purpose.

Pilot Test

It is important to ensure that the items in the questionnaires are consistent with the construct definition. Since all items that were employed in the current study were established through the adoption of validated instruments by previous researchers, the content validity is established. With the validity established, the instrument then underwent a pre-testing phases using a sample size of 50 Malaysians general adults. This is to ensure explicitness with the wording of the measurements and the items are easily understood by the respondents. Any inaccuracies and inadequacies are corrected before the actual field research is conducted.

During the pilot test, a preliminary reliability assessment was conducted using the Cronbach Alpha coefficient reliability test (Malhorta 2004). Overall, the alpha scores for all main constructs exceeded the benchmark of 0.70. Rectifications were made based on the feedback of the respondents which includes sentence structure and choice of words has been enhanced; and an additional instruction was included in the 'General Instructions' (i.e., "Some of the questions may appear to be similar, but they do address somewhat different issues"). It was conducted through factor analysis in examining reliability and validity (Cronbach's Alpha) for consistency, mean, standard deviation and multiple regressions as a means to find the relationship between the variables.

RESULTS

Correlation

Pearson's correlation coefficient is used to examine the independent and dependent variables of the proposed model. It measures the strength between the independent variables and dependent variables (Evans et al., 1996). It also attempts to draw a line of the best fit through the data of two variables and Pearson's correlation coefficient, it indicates how far away all these data are to the line of best fit.

The following Table 4.1 and 4.2 displays the descriptive statistics and the correlation coefficients respectively for all six variables. While Table 4.1 displays the means and standard deviations of all six variables. Table 4.2 shows the coefficients of all the variables involved, with regards to their degree of correlational relationship, together with the directions of said correlations – which in turn can also accept or reject the proposed hypotheses of this present paper.

According to Tables 4.1 and 4.2, It also shows that brand image ($M = 15.89$, $S.D. = 5.81$) had a significantly positive relationship with revisiting intentions ($M = 9.89$, $S.D. = 3.20$), $r(379) = 0.812$, $p < 0.001$. This allows the researcher to state that H_1 , which proposed that brand image has positive relationship with intention towards food trucks can be accepted. From the same set of tables, it can be seen that brand loyalty ($M = 12.78$, $S.D. = 4.34$) had a significantly positive relationship with revisiting intentions ($M = 9.89$, $S.D. = 3.20$), $r(379) = 0.924$, $p < 0.001$, allowing the researcher to conclude that H_2 , which proposed that brand loyalty has positive relationship with intention towards food trucks can be accepted.

Next, it shows that brand awareness (M = 9.50, S.D. = 3.30) had a significantly positive relationship with revisiting intentions (M = 9.89, S.D. = 3.20), $r(379) = 0.786$, $p < 0.001$. This can be concluded that H₃ which proposed that brand awareness has positive relationship with intention towards food trucks can be accepted. The following set of variables show that brand association (M = 13.70, S.D. = 4.13) had a significantly positive relationship with revisiting intentions (M = 9.89, S.D. = 3.20), $r(379) = 0.860$, $p < 0.001$, meaning that H₄, which proposed that brand association has positive relationship with intention towards food trucks can be accepted. And lastly, it can be seen that perceived price (M = 13.47, S.D. = 4.62) had a significantly positive relationship with revisiting intentions (M = 9.89, S.D. = 3.20), $r(379) = 0.925$, $p < 0.001$, showing that H₅, which proposed that perceived price has positive relationship with intention towards food trucks can be accepted.

Table 4.1: Descriptive statistics of all variables

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Revisit Intention	9.8918	3.20324	379
Brand Image	15.8865	5.80779	379
Brand Loyalty	12.7757	4.34002	379
Brand Awareness	9.5040	3.30173	379
Brand Association	13.6966	4.13083	379
Price	13.4670	4.61718	379

Table 4.2: Pearson correlation coefficient of all variable

		Brand Image	Brand Loyalty	Brand Awareness	Brand Association	Price	Revisit Intention
Brand Image	Pearson Correlation	1	.787**	.804**	.756**	.693**	.812**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	379	379	379	379	379	379
Brand Loyalty	Pearson Correlation		1	.850**	.773**	.909**	.924**
	Sig. (2-tailed)			.000	.000	.000	.000
	N		379	379	379	379	379
Brand Awareness	Pearson Correlation			1	.688**	.772**	.786**
	Sig. (2-tailed)				.000	.000	.000
	N			379	379	379	379
Brand Association	Pearson Correlation				1	.816**	.860**
	Sig. (2-tailed)					.000	.000
	N				379	379	379

Price	Pearson Correlation	1	.925**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	379	379
Revisit Intention	Pearson Correlation		1
	Sig. (2-tailed)		
	N		379

Regression Coefficients

Within a statistical analysis, a regression analysis can be conducted to estimate the extent of the relationships amongst variables. The following Table 4.3 – Table 4.5 will display the linear regression analyses conducted within this present paper on revisit intention. The first of these Tables is the Model Summary, which highlights the extent of the input predictors (i.e. IVs) on the resulting variance of the DV, using a step-wise method, incrementally adding more IVs in, starting from price, to brand image, to brand loyalty, to brand association and finally, brand awareness. In doing so (step-wise), one can observe the differences in the R² value as to explain the variances of the DV. When reviewing Table 4.3, it can be observed that as more of the IVs are taken into account, the R² value also increases, upwards to 0.932, thus allowing the researcher to conclude that 93.2% of the changes in the variance of the DV (revisit intention) is significant affected ($p < 0.001$) by the predictors (IVs). In Table 4.4, the ANOVA results reflect the findings of the Model Summary, with all 5 models (input of all 5 IVs in incremental steps) showcasing significant p-values of < 0.001 .

Table 4.3: Model summary of the valid variables against revisit intention

Model	R	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	Change Statistics			Sig. F Change	Durbin-Watson	
					F Change	df1	df2			
1	.925 ^a	.855	.855	1.22035	.855	2227.360	1	377	.000	
2	.955 ^b	.912	.911	.95509	.056	239.496	1	376	.000	
3	.959 ^c	.919	.919	.91380	.008	35.744	1	375	.000	
4	.964 ^d	.929	.928	.85978	.009	49.608	1	374	.000	
5	.965 ^e	.932	.931	.84034	.003	18.503	1	373	.000	2.204

Table 4.4: ANOVA of the valid variables against revisit intention

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	3317.114	1	3317.114	2227.360	.000 ^b
	Residual	561.450	377	1.489		
	Total	3878.565	378			
2	Regression	3535.580	2	1767.790	1937.959	.000 ^c
	Residual	342.984	376	.912		
	Total	3878.565	378			

3	Regression	3565.428	3	1188.476	1423.272	.000 ^d
	Residual	313.137	375	.835		
	Total	3878.565	378			
4	Regression	3602.099	4	900.525	1218.220	.000 ^e
	Residual	276.466	374	.739		
	Total	3878.565	378			
5	Regression	3615.165	5	723.033	1023.886	.000 ^f
	Residual	263.400	373	.706		
	Total	3878.565	378			

Table 4.5: Regression Coefficients of the valid variables against revisit intention

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
1 (Constant)	1.252	.194		6.467	.000
Price	.642	.014	.925	47.195	.000
2 (Constant)	.499	.159		3.135	.002
Price	.483	.015	.697	32.745	.000
Brand Image	.182	.012	.329	15.476	.000
3 (Constant)	.438	.153		2.873	.004
Price	.363	.025	.523	14.774	.000
Brand Image	.141	.013	.255	10.681	.000
Brand Loyalty					.000
	.183	.031	.247	5.979	
4 (Constant)	.016	.156		.102	.919
Price	.269	.027	.388	10.070	.000
Brand Image	.095	.014	.173	6.844	.000
Brand Loyalty	.212	.029	.287	7.304	.000
Brand Association	.148	.021	.191	7.043	.000
5 (Constant)	.128	.154		.830	.407
Price	.278	.026	.401	10.627	.000
Brand Image	.122	.015	.222	8.159	.000
Brand Loyalty	.258	.030	.350	8.509	.000
Brand Association	.139	.021	.179	6.703	.000
Brand Awareness	-.118	.027	-.122	-4.301	.000

A multiple regression analysis was conducted as can be seen in Table 4.5, with the purpose of investigating the extent of the predictability of the independent variables (brand image, brand loyalty, brand awareness, brand association and price) on the dependent variable (revisiting intentions). Even via utilizing the stepwise method of elimination for variables (taking out non-significant variables), all five of the independent variables were accounted for: brand image, brand loyalty, brand awareness, brand association and price. A significant regression was found with $F(5, 373) = 1023.886$, $p < 0.001$, alongside an R^2 of 0.932, which implies that 93.2% of all five independent variables accounted for the dependent variable revisiting intentions. As for the regression coefficients, it can be observed that revisiting intentions is

equivalent to $0.128 + 0.278$ (price) + 0.122 (brand image) + 0.258 (brand loyalty) + 0.139 (brand association) – 0.118 (brand awareness), as brand awareness shows $t(-4.301) = -0.118$, $p < 0.001$, brand association shows $t(6.703) = 0.139$, $p < 0.001$, brand loyalty shows $t(8.509) = 0.258$, $p < 0.001$, brand image show $t(8.159) = 0.122$, $p < 0.001$, and price shows $t(10.627) = 0.278$, $p < 0.001$, all of which had significant p-values.

Discussion on Research Objectives and Research Questions

From the in-depth analysis of the database that was collected several conclusions can be made as to the research questions and hypotheses that were proposed by this researcher. A summary of the findings from the reliability values, to the correlations, and regression coefficients can be shown in the following Table 4.6 – Table 4.8, with their implications towards this present paper’s propositions. To summarise, all items tested were found to be normally distributed, with high reliabilities of Cronbach’s Alpha values being above 0.7. When testing for their correlational relationships, the findings were able to showcase a positive correlation between all IVs and the DV in question. With that said, it was concluded that brand image, brand loyalty, brand awareness, brand association and perceived price were all significantly and positively correlated with revisiting intentions. After conducting a regression analysis on the results, it was found that 93.2% of revisit intentions can be attributed to the IVs in question (brand image, brand loyalty, brand awareness, brand association and perceived price), which were able to significantly predict the level of revisit intentions through a regression formula as shown in Table 4.8 below. These findings and their implications are discussed in the following section.

Table 4.6: Reliabilities of all variables

Variable	Cronbach’s Alpha	Reliability
Revisiting Intentions	0.980	Highly Reliable
Brand Image	0.939	Highly Reliable
Brand Loyalty	0.908	Highly Reliable
Brand Awareness	0.926	Highly Reliable
Brand Association	0.932	Highly Reliable
Perceived Price	0.979	Highly Reliable

Table 4.7: Correlational direction and significance of all hypotheses

Correlation	Significance	Hypotheses Tests
Positive	$r(379) = 0.791, p < 0.001$	H1 Accepted
Positive	$r(379) = 0.812, p < 0.001$	H2 Accepted
Positive	$r(379) = 0.924, p < 0.001$	H3 Accepted
Positive	$r(379) = 0.786, p < 0.001$	H4 Accepted
Positive	$r(379) = 0.860, p < 0.001$	H5 Accepted

Table 4.8: Regression coefficients for target variables revisiting intentions

Dependent (Target) Variable	Regression
Revisiting Intentions	$0.128 + 0.278 (\text{price}) + 0.122 (\text{brand image}) + 0.258 (\text{brand loyalty}) + 0.139 (\text{brand association}) - 0.118 (\text{brand awareness})$

CONCLUSION

The findings from this present paper was able to accept the proposed hypothesis on the positive relationship between brand loyalty and revisit intention, which was in turn based on the findings of both Assael (1992), and Samuelsen and Sanvik (1997). As consumers get used to supporting one brand above another, their perceived value of said brand not only increases, but their rejection of alternatives also increases alongside. With that in mind, the proposed hypothesis which stated the positive relationship between brand loyalty and intention towards food truck was found to be accepted in this present paper, further emphasising the role that brand loyalty plays. As brands are found to have an easier time retaining old customers instead of finding new ones (Yoo, Donthu & Lee, 2000), the findings of this paper showed support for the conclusions made by Supphellen and Nysveen (2001), which supposed that the drivers of intention to revisit can be found alongside brand loyalty as well.

Not only is brand awareness a noticeable factor that influences revisit intention, it is also found to be instrumental in creating revisit intentions as noted by Kim et al (2009). The essential knowledge of a brand can also be associated with the potential for consumers to build their revisit intention in regards to said brands, whereby the role of brand awareness also covets the role it plays in creating positive brand revisit intention. This association was observed in the findings of this present paper, whereby not only was brand awareness privy to the formation of revisit intentions, it was found to be an important part of a regression formula that can predict said revisit intentions. And as such, the proposed hypotheses whereby brand awareness was positively related to revisit intention was proven to be accepted in this present paper.

Similarly, this same act of association of a brand will also in turn affect how often, or how much consumers support these brands, through the build-up of revisit intention (Ryu, Lee & Gon Kim, 2012), a conclusion that was also supported by the findings of this present paper. As potential and actual consumers begin to think more often about a brand through brand association, the chances of revisiting intention also grow alongside. In this sense, the proposed hypotheses of this present paper, which stated that there a positive relationship between brand association and revisit intention, is accepted, supported by the findings of this present paper, and that of other past papers as stated above.

For as long as a brand is appealing to the public, there is a good chance for the formation of brand equity, which in turn also affects revisiting intentions, as noted by several past papers (Chew & Jahari, 2014; Burmann et al., 2008; Ryu, Lee & Gon Kim, 2012). This association was found to be predictable, especially for revisiting intentions, which included the variable brand image as a factor for the regression of revisiting intentions as found within this present paper.

The studies of Iglesias and Guillen (2004) and Hermann, Xia, Monroe and Huber (2007) have indicated that consumers perceive a greater risk when purchasing products and services that are pricey over the low-priced items, which also happens to generate revisit intention via association, as noted by Raza et al (2012), whereby the perceived quality, value and eventual satisfaction has been found to be very much affected by the price of the product or service, thus quantifying how much one pays, to how much value the price means. This was similarly shown in the findings of this present paper, with price playing an integral role in the formation of revisit intention. And as such, the proposed hypotheses of this present paper, which stated the positive relationship between price and intention towards food trucks is accepted, supported by the evidence collected.

One of the limitations that can be identified within this present paper is the sample size and scope, which was limited to only the Klang Valley. As noted by the Malaysian Digest (2016), the market for food trucks stands in the billions, with many other major cities of Malaysia understudied, much like Kuala Lumpur. As a relatively new phenomenon, the concept of food trucks, and the consumer behaviours associated with said food trucks remain to be an open invitation for more research and investigation. Not only was the sample used within this paper limited, the scope was limited to just one city, which can restrict the findings, as those from Klang Valley come from vastly different socioeconomic backgrounds from those in Penang Island for example.

Consequently, as we focus on the difference in perspectives and opinions of the targeted sample for this present paper, the utilization of a quantitative research method may not be enough to fully comprehend the food truck phenomenon as such. While a quantitative research paper is able to extract statistical data from the collected dataset of the targeted sample, it is not enough to form a more in-depth understanding of the consumers of food trucks in this case. As explained on a paper based on the advantages and usage of qualitative research methodologies by Baxter and Jack (2008), there are many aspects of a qualitative paper that a quantitative paper such as this present one, cannot provide. The associated perspectives, opinions, commentaries and even suggestions from a qualitative research paper would allow this researcher to conduct a study that truly explores the factors that affects brand equity and revisit intentions in a more personalized manner, closer to the ground as such.

Last but not least, this present paper was also conducted with already established factors that may or may not affect both brand equity and revisit intentions. As noted by various past papers (Yoo & Donthu 2000, Netemeyer et al. 2004, Erdem et al. 2006), the concept of brand equity is already confusing in its definition and association. With this in mind, by restricting the scope of research in terms of the factors or independent variables as done within this present paper, there is a possibility that much more significant aspects are missed such as influence of family and friends, the role of marketing or advertisements for example. In this sense, while this paper was able to find many associations of brand image, brand loyalty, brand awareness, brand association and price towards brand equity and revisit intention, there could also be additional factors that could have played a much more significant role in this regard.

A wider scope of study should be conducted for future papers based on this subject, with a larger target sample, across different socioeconomic backgrounds, and even different cities, in association with the food truck phenomenon. Not only that, a more personalized form of research should be conducted via a qualitative research method, thereby extracting opinions and perspectives of the target sample. By conducting such a type of research, future papers on

this subject may formulate a stronger, more solid research paper on the factors that truly affects or impacts the brand equity and revisit intention in association with food trucks.

As typical Malaysians who are spoiled for choice when it comes to food and beverage, future studies can focus on what drives Malaysian consumers in regards to such social phenomenon such as food trucks. By understanding how Malaysian consumers think and feel, and therefore, predicting their behaviours, those within the industry can perform actions that fulfils the market demands appropriately, leveraging on the 'needs' and 'wants' of their consumers, potential or otherwise.

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